

The effect of vitamin and mineral premix feed additives on the control slaughter indicators of male lambs

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The research was conducted to learn the effect of vitamin and vitamin-mineral feed additives on the control slaughter indicators of 9 male lambs of the Bozakh breed placed in their rumen cannulas. The addition of vitamins and vitamin-mineral premixes to the male lamb's ration has a positive effect on the control slaughter indicators. Thus, mentioned feed additives caused a significant increase in the control slaughter indicators of male lambs - slaughter weight, carcass weight, and carcass yield. It was also found that the feed additives caused a reliable increase in the morphological composition of the carcass during slaughter in experimental animals. Therefore, the addition of vitamin and vitamin-mineral premix supplements to the ration has a positive effect on control slaughter indicators of male lambs.

Keywords: *Male lambs, control slaughter, slaughter weight, carcass weight, carcass yield, vitamins, minerals, premixes*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, one of the main goals in the intensive development of sheep farming is to increase the productivity of meat, milk, and wool under proper feeding conditions. Therefore, it is very important to use a good feed base and balanced feed portions with the addition of biologically active substances (Pozov, 2013; Talybov, 2009). Since young animals have a high metabolism, they need to receive these nutrients regularly. Accordingly, the additives of the mentioned nutrients to the feed ration of lambs and muttons are also important for fully revealing the genetic potential of the animals (Gavryushina, 2010; Abdullah, Kridli, Shaker, et al. 2010; Assan, 2015; Bellof, Pallauf, 2007; Carneiro, Louvandini, Paiva, et al. 2010). In this regard, the current stage of the research aimed to reveal the effect of vitamin and vitamin-mineral supplements on the control slaughter indicators of fattening male lambs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was performed on the basis of SRIAH and ASAU. The experiments were carried out on 6-month-old male lambs of the Bozakh breed. According to a similar principle, 9 lambs were selected (~31 kg. BW) and divided into 3 equal groups. A month before the start of the experiments, ruminal cannulas were implanted in

all experimental animals using the A.A. Aliyev method (Aliyev, 1998). The experiments are shown in Table 1.

As shown in the table, the animals in group I according to the main food ration (MFR), received grass, barley, and cottonseed meal. The lambs in the II experimental group received an extra 0.5 g. of vitamin supplement – Supervit Forte and the III experimental group of lambs received an extra 0.5 ml. of vitamin and mineral premixes each in addition to MFR per day.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To obtain complete information about meat productivity and meat quality of animals, control slaughter should be carried out and its indicators should be analyzed. Based on the control slaughter indicators of the control group of male lambs, it can be said that vitamin and vitamin-mineral supplements have a sufficient effect on these indicators and ensure the formation of high meat productivity (Table 2). As can be seen from the Table 2, the weight of the cold carcass in groups II and III was higher than in the control group by 3.9% and 6.2% respectively. However, the highest result for this indicator of the carcass weight is observed in group III with 18.5 kg. The carcass weight in the II and III groups are higher than control group indicators 24.5 % (P<0.01) and 29.4% (P<0.05) respectively.

Table 1. Experiment scheme

Groups	Number of animals	Feeding conditions
I Control group	3	1.7 kg. of hay, 200 g. of barley, 100 g. of cottonseed meal.
II Experimental group	3	MFR + 1 g. baker's yeast.
III Experimental group	3	MFR + 3 g. baker's yeast.

Table 2. Control slaughter indicators of experimental lambs

Indicators	Groups		
	I	II	III
Number of animals in groups	3	3	3
Pre-slaughter live mass, kg	38,8±0,84	40,3±1,10	41,2±1,06
Carcass weight, kg	14,3±0,16	17,8±0,30**	18,5±0,29**
Tail fat mass, kg	3,2±0,09	3,8±0,10	4,0±0,13
Mass of visceral fat, kg	0,49±0,01	0,61±0,02	0,63±0,02
Slaughter mass, kg	18,0±0,32	22,2±0,35**	23,1±0,30**
Yield of carcass, kg	46,4±0,44	55,1±0,47**	56,1±0,39**
Morphological composition of the carcass, kg: soft meat	11,6±0,21	13,3±0,30*	13,8±0,40*
Bones	3,9±0,10	4,1±0,15	4,2±0,20
Meat to bone ratio (1 kg)	3,0	3,2	3,3

Note: * - $P < 0,05$; ** - $P < 0,01$ (according to control group)

Cutting the carcass and removing the meat from the bones began after keeping the carcass in the refrigerator for 24 hours (+5°C). As can be seen from the table, the amount of tail fat and visceral fat in the II and III groups are 18.8% and 25% respectively, higher than group I indicators. Almost the same results are observed for fat mass. These indicators are 24.5% and 28.6% higher than the I group indicator, respectively.

In addition to all this, during the slaughter, the carcass is divided into parts, and the meat is separated from the bones. The main criteria are carcass weight, carcass yield, and meat softness quantity. As can be seen from the table, significant differences were recorded between the experimental and control groups according to the indicated indicators. The highest result of slaughter weight was observed in group III and was 23.1 kg. This indicator was 28.3% ($P < 0.01$) higher than the indicator of the control group, and 4% higher than the II group. Further, the highest result for slaughter yield was observed in group III animals and was 56.1%. This is 20.9% ($p < 0.01$) and 1.8% higher than the control and the II groups, respectively. Similar results were recorded for the amount of soft meat. The amount of soft meat in the II and III groups animals was 14.7% ($P < 0.05$) and 19% ($P < 0.05$) higher than in the control group animals, respectively.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our studies show that additives of vitamins and vitamin-mineral premixes to the feed ration of fattening male lambs significantly

improve their control slaughter indicators. Thus, the mentioned feed supplements led to a reliable increase in the carcass weight, slaughter weight, carcass yield, and the amount of soft meat in the control group. In addition, it was determined that the mentioned feed additives significantly increase the amount of tail and visceral fat in experimental animals.

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Yem payına vitamin-mineral tərkibli premikslərin əlavə edilməsinin erkək toğluların nəzarət kəsiminin göstəricilərinə təsiri

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Tədqiqatın məqsədi vitamin və vitamin-mineral yem əlavələrinin erkək quzuların nəzarət kəsim göstəricilərinə təsirini araşdırmaq olmuşdur. Tədqiqatda Bozax cinsindən olan 9 baş erkək quzular ilə aparılmışdır. Quzuların rasionuna vitamin və vitamin-mineral premikslərinin əlavə edilməsi nəzarət kəsim göstəricilərinə müsbət təsir göstərmişdir. Yem əlavələri kəsim çəkisinin, karkasın çəkisinin və cəmdək məhsuldarlığının əhəmiyyətli dərəcədə artması ilə nəticələndi. Karkasın morfoloji tərkibi də eksperimental heyvanlarda etibarlı artım göstərmişdir. Buna görə də quzuların qida rasionuna vitamin və vitamin-mineral premiks əlavələrinin daxil edilməsi nəzarət kəsim göstəricilərinə müsbət təsir göstərmişdir.

Açar sözlər: *Erkək toğlular, nəzarət kəsimi, buğlu cəmdək, kəsim kütləsi, kəsim çıxarı, vitaminlər, minerallar, premikslər*